

UZBEK NATIONAL WRESTLING

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ABSTRACT

An in-depth study of the millennial history of Kurash confirms that Kurash has indeed been honored and valued as an example of the physical and spiritual maturity of wrestlers. Therefore, wrestlers have physical strength, youthful stature or fighting, mobility, agility, dexterity, how to behave in a wide circle, morality, morality, attitude to the opponent, patriotism, attitude to society and the environment. 'rin holds.

INTRODUCTION

Wrestling is one of the national sports. He is gaining popularity and fame all over the world. The struggle that has fascinated millions also has deep historical roots as one of the world's highest spiritual values. Material evidence found as a result of research, studies and archeological scientific researches and aspirations of historians, archeologists and philosophers proves that the age of Kurash is at least 2.5-3 thousand years. Rare finds in the Surkhandarya, Zarafshan oases and a number of ancient settlements of the Fergana Valley, as well as rock art samples testify to this. "There are six artefacts that scientifically prove the history of our wrestling. For example, a mural of two wrestlers found in Panjikent is a unique monument to the Sogdian statehood, ie the Middle Ages.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

There are reports that many of the saints of our people fought. For example, the shrine of Sheikh Khudaiddod Azizon in the village of Gazira in the Jonboy district of Samarkand region is a sacred shrine. So, who is Sheikh Khudaiddod Azizon? According to B.Valikhodjayev, B.Urinbaev's pamphlet "Khudoydodi Vali", the father of the great saint Sheikh Khudaydod Azizon later moved to Karmana, and finally two farsahs (about 6-8 km) east of the city in a village. rnashadi. It was in this village in 1462 that a boy was born in the house of the old sheikh Ortiq, who was named Khudoiberdi. Educated at a village school, Khudoiberdi warmly welcomed Sheikh Jamoliddin Khudoiberdi, a leading figure of the Yassavi sect, in Bukhara in 1480 and nicknamed him "Khudoydod" (Khudoiberdi's Tajik). Educated in

Samarkand, Gijduvan and Bukhara madrasas, Khudoiberdi went to Karmana in 1484 and to the capital Bukhara in the early years of Karmana when he heard about the oppression of the people by the Karnabdashti begi in the south of Karmana. After gathering all the country's wrestlers for the fight, the ruler of Bukhara, Temuridzoda, told Muhammad Baqi Mirzo what he wanted for the prize, and Baba Khudoydod asked the governor to remove Garnab Begi from office. After the removal of the ruler Zoli from the post of the head of the nation, the people of the steppe villages will be free from oppression. Sheikh Khudaiddod Azizon, who moved to Samarkand in the early 1500s, died in 1532. Manoqibi Sheikh Khudaydoda Azizon, a biography of the sheikh and baklavan, is now in the hands of generations and in the funds of Uzbekistan. At the same time, there are reports that the great representative of Naqshbandi, Sayyid Amir Kulol (lived 1301-1372), also fought, and his grave is now located in the village of Sukhor in Kagan district.

In general, the information about the thousands of heroes of the national centuries and even earlier, stored in the treasures and archives of ancient manuscripts of Uzbekistan, awaits its researchers. In particular, the Risale-i Ghostangiri (The Treatise of the Wrestlers) has been preserved, which is described in detail in terms of the faith and etiquette of the wrestlers.

DISCUSSION

After Uzbekistan gained independence, attention was focused on the national struggle. The new rules for national wrestling incorporate the most revered traditions of Uzbek wrestling and international sports standards, such as

special clothing, the venue, and the duration of the competition. Sports experts acknowledged that the rules of wrestling, developed by Komil Yusupov, fully meet the requirements of international sports. One of the main advantages of wrestling rules is that they do not allow the fight to continue while lying down.

As soon as one of the athletes touches the carpet, the referee stops the competition and the wrestlers continue the competition standing. This ensures that the fight is fast and interesting for the fans. In addition, the rules of wrestling prohibit the use of methods that hold the lower part of the belt or cause pain and suffocation. Thus, wrestling has become one of the safest sports to prevent injuries to athletes. Uzbekistan's declaration of independence in 1991 gave new life to the struggle. As a result of these efforts, representatives of about 30 countries took part in the first international wrestling competitions in Tashkent, the capital of Uzbekistan. The 30,000-seat stadium in central Tashkent is packed. Millions of TV viewers in Uzbekistan and abroad watched the competitions in detail on television. Wrestling is one of the oldest types of wrestling. At the same time, it is the youngest sport on the world stage. Despite its long history, wrestling only made its mark on the world sports scene in 1998. These steps are neither easy nor short. From the very beginning, the bright steps of the struggle and the goal expected of it were clearly defined. It is to turn Uzbek wrestling into an international sport.

CONCLUSION

It should be noted that our national wrestling, first of all, is honored as an example of all-round maturity of wrestlers. Their physical strength, stature,

fighting spirit, agility, one-sidedness, wide-ranging behavior, manners, spiritual appearance, attitude to the opponent, the environment are in a special place. It has also been a sacred tradition to follow untouched warriors as piru masters and to follow the teachings of the pandu. A clear example of our idea is the famous Khorezmian poet and wrestler Pahlavon Mahmud. It is important to strengthen the feelings of patriotism and national pride in

the hearts of the younger generation, to bring them up in a physically healthy and spiritually harmonious way. Taking into account these aspects, all kinds of sports in our country are given attention at the level of state policy. In particular, on November 4, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution "On measures to develop the national sport of wrestling and further enhance its international prestige".

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